

Synthesis and NMR characterization of ZSM-35

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Abstract : ZSM-35 and Ferrierite were synthesized using ethylene diamine and pyrrolidine as templating agents. X-Ray diffraction, Scanning electron micrograph, Fourier transform - Infrared spectroscopy and surface area analysis indicate the synthesized samples were highly crystalline. ^{27}Al Magic angle spinning nuclear magnetic resonance spectroscopic results show that the ZSM-35 and Ferrierite contain tetrahedrally coordinated aluminium atoms. Four environmentally different tetrahedral aluminum species are observed through triple quantum ^{27}Al magic angle spinning nuclear magnetic resonance spectroscopic analysis. Similar to tetrahedral aluminum species four different environmentally different sodium species are also observed. The ^{29}Si MAS NMR studies shows ZSM-35 have two different silicon species and Ferrierite has three species.

Keywords : ZSM-35, Ferrierite, isomorphous, XRD, SEM, FT-IR, MAS NMR, 3-Q MAS NMR.

Introduction

ZSM-35 is a medium pore molecular sieve, which has extensive applications in the petrochemical industry. Originally patented by Mobil (US 4,016, 245 (1977))¹, this zeolite can be synthesized hydrothermally using pyrrolidine and ethylene diamine templates¹⁻⁶. Although the complete X-ray structure determination of ZSM-35 is not available, the strikingly similar X-ray diffraction powder spectrum of ZSM-35 to that of Ferrierite suggests that its structure is of Ferrierite type. Apart from this, there has been no experimental evidence to show that these two structures are indeed isomorphic. For Ferrierite, all the atomic co-ordinates have been determined for the natural mineral, the orthorhombic structure consists of chains of five member rings that are parallel to the c-axis and are cross (-) linked by four membered rings with the main ten membered ring channels, lying along [001] with the intersection along [010]. The building units of Ferrierite⁷⁻⁹ contain four unique tetrahedral sites, which in a siliceous material are occupied only by Si. The Al occupation at all the four T-sites is however less probable in synthetic Ferrierite since Si/Al is typically in the range 30 to 200¹⁰. In the case of ZSM-35¹¹, for which synthetic preparations can yield materials with Si/Al 7.6 and above, one can expect that these T-sites would be occupied by Al

when Si/Al is low (*ca.* 7.6). Similarly, for the zeolite, namely, Na-ZSM-35, the charge on the framework is neutralized by sodium cations, leading to nonequivalence among sodiums residing in the cationic positions¹². Thus, a one to one mapping of the Al and Na sites in ZSM-35 and a comparison of the experimental results with those obtained on Ferrierite, would provide valuable structural insights about ZSM-35.

The present study focuses on delineating the structural features of ZSM-35 using multinuclear solid state MAS/MQ-MAS NMR. MAS (^{29}Si) and 3Q-MAS (^{27}Al) NMR will be used to elucidate the framework environments, while ^{23}Na triple quantum experiments will be used for the characterization of nonframework cationic positions. Further a quantification of MAS and 3-Q MAS results lead to the determination of structurally significant chemical shift (δ_{cs}) and quadrupole interaction (P_Q) parameters.

Experimental

In a typical procedure to synthesize ZSM-35, 3.3 g of sodium aluminate (99%, sid. fine, India) was mixed well with 0.7 g of sodium hydroxide (99%, s.d. fine, India) and 129 g of distilled water. This mixture was stirred well until the entire solid is dissolved. This was taken as

solution A. Another solution B was made by thorough mixing of 46.47 g of silica sol (30%, s.d. fine, India) and ethylene diamine (18.3 g, C₂DN, 99%, Aldrich, USA). Solutions A and B were mixed well to make clear mixture (1.85Na₂O : Al₂O₃ : 15.2SiO₂ : 592H₂O : 19.7C₂DN) and charged into a teflon lined steel autoclave. Crystallization was carried out at 177 °C for 10 days. The product was removed and washed with deionised water and the sample was dried at 110 °C for 24 h. The zeolite so prepared was subjected to various physicochemical characterizations.

Synthesis of Ferrierite : 52.5 g of sodium silicate (in 25 ml of distilled water) was stirred with 10 ml pyrrolidine. To this solution, 2.4 g of aluminium sulphate hexadecahydrate (in 25 ml distilled water) and 1.8 g of sulphuric acid (in 10 ml distilled water) were added. Finally, 30 ml of distilled water was added and the gel (pH = 11.5 ± 0.2) was stirred vigorously for 2 h and autoclaved in a 300 ml stainless steel Parr autoclave (4842, 300 ml) and heated at 160 °C for 60 h. The initial gel composition was, 20Na₂O : Al₂O₃ : 37Pyrrolidine : 66.5SiO₂ : 6.3H₂SO₄ : 1460H₂O. The autoclave was quenched, filtered, washed and product was dried at 110 °C for 6–8 h. The resulting material was calcined in air at 550 °C for 18–20 h.

X-Ray diffraction patterns were recorded on a Rigaku (D/MAX III VC) instrument in the 2θ region of 5–45°. Scanning electron microscope pictures were taken using a Jeol JSM 5200 microscope. Chemical analysis was carried out by XRF using a Rigaku 3070 X-ray spectrometer. The framework IR spectra were recorded in the diffuse reflectance mode using 300 : 1 ratio sample in KBr (Nicolet 60SXB). BET surface area analysis was carried out using Micromeritics Tristar surface area and Porosity analyzer.

²⁷Al MAS/3-Q MAS solid state NMR experiments were performed on a Bruker DRX-500 FT-NMR spectrometer, at the resonance frequencies of 130.287 MHz (²⁷Al), 132.256 MHz (²³Na) respectively. ²⁹Si MAS NMR experiments were carried out on a Bruker MSL-300 NMR experiments at the resonance frequency 99.3 MHz (²⁹Si). The ²⁷Al, ²³Na triple quantum experiments were performed using a three pulse sequence incorporating a z-filter^{12,14}. The z-filter modification ensured that the echo and anti-echo pathways were symmetrised during the conversion step to get a pure absorption mode 2D spectra

with negligible phase distortion. MAS spinning speed of 13.5 KHz was employed along with rotor synchronization during the triple quantum evolution period (*t*₁) to eliminate spinning side bands appearing in the isotropic dimension. After a shearing, the ²³Na and ²⁷Al 3Q-MAS contour plots were analyzed by a graphical procedure¹⁵ to extract the chemical shift and quadrupolar interaction parameters¹⁵. ²⁹Si MAS spectra were acquired using a spinning speed of 4 KHz was employed. The signal positions in ²⁹Si MAS spectra are referenced with respect to TMS (external) while ²⁷Al MAS/3-Q MAS signal positions are referenced with respect to Al³⁺(H₂O)₆.

Table 1. Graphical analysis results for ²³Na in ZSM-35

Species	δ _{iso} (ppm)	P _Q (MHz)
Td ₁	-26.74	3.26
Td ₂	-29.21	3.09
Td ₃	-31.26	2.91
Td ₄	-34.01	2.49

Table 2. Graphical analysis results for ²⁷Al in ZSM-35

Species	δ _{iso} (ppm)	P _Q (MHz)
Td ₁	58.52	1.54
Td ₂	57.64	1.51
Td ₃	56.50	1.65
Td ₄	54.79	1.72

Results and discussion

The X-ray diffraction powder spectra of ZSM-35 and Ferrierite are shown in Fig. 1. The high crystallinity of ZSM-35 and Ferrierite is evidenced by sharp peaks in the

Fig. 1. X-Ray diffraction pattern of (a) ZSM-35 and (b) Ferrierite.

XRD spectra, The ZSM-35 and Ferrierite were further characterized by Scanning electron micrograph (Fig. 2), They reveal that the particle size (ZSM-35 = 10×15

Fig. 2. Scanning electron micrograph of (a)ZSM-35 and (b) Ferrierite.

μm and Ferrierite = $5 \mu\text{m}$) and shape (ZSM-35 = grain and Ferrierite = flower) were different. Fourier transform Infrared spectroscopic analysis (Fig. 3) indicates that these molecular sieves have T-O-T (T = Al or Si)

Fig. 3. FT-IR spectrum of (a) ZSM-35 and (b) Ferrierite.

asymmetric, symmetric (inner and outer), bending, double ring and pore opening vibrations. The chemical analysis gives Si/Al = 11 for ZSM-35 and 50 for Ferrierite. The BET surface area was determined to be 400 and 360 cm^2/g for ZSM-35 and Ferrierite, respectively.

Fig. 4 shows the ^{29}Si MAS NMR spectra of ZSM-35 (A) and Ferrierite (B). The increased signal resolution in Ferrierite is readily apparent and is attributable to the weaker Si...Al dipolar interactions, owing to its higher Si/Al, being removed by MAS. The multiplicity of signals in the -106.97 to -114.83 ppm range is due to the

Fig. 4. ^{29}Si MAS NMR spectrum of (a) ZSM-35 and (b) Ferrierite.

crystallographic nonequivalence and the signal assignments follow previous report¹⁵. In the case of ZSM-35 the larger linewidth precludes this distinction. However, signals in the ppm range -114.83 to 112.54 , due to Q_4 (4SiAl) could be identified from the spectral deconvolution. In both ZSM-35 and Ferrierite we observed the Si resonance at -106.97 ppm due to Q_3 (3SiAl) environments. The higher intensity for this peak in the case of ZSM-35 is due to a lower Si/Al. By a deconvolution of ^{29}Si MAS spectra and estimating the integrated intensities for Q_4 (0Al) and Q_3 (1Al) silicon resonances, which estimate the framework Si/Al to be 8.36 and 30.6 for ZSM-35 and Ferrierite respectively.

Fig. 5 shows the comparison of ^{27}Al MAS spectra of ZSM-35/Ferrierite. These spectra depict Al purely in tetrahedral co-ordination due to the appearance of signals in

Fig. 5. ^{27}Al MAS NMR spectrum of ZSM-35/Ferrierite.

the 6.411 to 51.0 ppm region. However no clues are provided about the signal multiplicity due to crystallographic nonequivalence. This is due to residual second order quadrupolar broadening, which is not eliminated under MAS. The residual second order quadrupolar broadening is eliminated in the triple quantum MAS experiment (Figs. 6 and 7). This is achieved by a two dimensional correlation of orientation dependent triple quan-

are readily determined for 3Q-MAS spectra¹⁵. Four different splitting in the 3Q-MAS NMR is appeared for inequivalent tetrahedrally coordinated aluminium. The δ_{iso} values for ZSM-35, the Td₁ to Td₄ species were decreased from 58.52 to 54.79 ppm. The same molecular sieve increased for P_Q was increased from 1.54 to 1.72 MHz. The contour in ZSM-35 and Ferrierite are situated in same position and in both zeolites aluminium is located in

Fig. 6. ²⁷Al 3-Q MAS (a) and ²³Na 3-Q MAS (b) spectrum of ZSM-35.

Fig. 7. ²⁷Al 3-Q MAS (a) and ²³Na 3-Q MAS (b) spectrum of Ferrierite.

tum frequencies with the corresponding single quantum frequencies detected during the acquisition period (t_2). After scaling, the center of gravity of the contour is located at (54,56) and (54,56) and the chemical shift (δ_{cs}) and the second order quadrupole shift (P_Q) parameters

same environment. This is in similar to the ²⁷Al MAS NMR result.

Figs. 6 and 7 shows the comparison of ²³Na 3-Q MAS NMR spectrum of ZSM-35 and Ferrierite. The residual second order quadrupolar broadening is eliminated in the

triple quantum MAS experiment. This is achieved by a two dimensional correlation of orientation dependent triple quantum frequencies with the corresponding single quantum frequencies detected during the acquisition period. After scaling the center of gravity of the contour is located at (12,32) and (8,5) and the chemical shift (δ_{cs}) and the second order quadrupole shift (P_Q) parameters are readily determined for 3-Q MAS spectra¹⁴. Four different splitting in the 3-Q MAS are appeared for environmentally different sodium. The δ_{iso} values for ZSM-35, Td₁ to Td₄ species were decreased from -26.74 to -34.01 ppm. The P_Q values for same were decreased from 3.26 to 2.49 MHz.

Conclusions :

ZSM-35 and Ferrierite were synthesized using ethylene diamine and pyrrolidine templates. XRD, SEM, FT-IR and surface area analysis shows that the synthesized sample were highly crystalline. ²⁷Al MAS NMR indicate that the aluminium in ZSM-35 and Ferrierite are present in tetrahedral co-ordination. However the chemical shifts values are different. This may be due to the difference is a-axis of the unit cell. ²⁹Si MAS NMR shows that the presence of two different species in ZSM-35 and three different species in Ferrierite samples. ²⁷Al and ²³Na 3-Q MAS NMR of ZSM-35 and Ferrierite show the presence of four crystallographically distinct species.

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